

A Study On Impact Of In-Tunnel Advertising With Special Reference To Namma Metro In-Tunnel Near Vidhana Soudha, Bangalore.

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ABSTRACT:*In-tunnel advertising is a great, creative and innovative advertising idea. An in-tunnel advertising system consists of series of back-lit poster images to create the illusion of a motion picture advertisement screened in the train carriage window. These posters with consecutive frames of a movie are hanged out next to each other on the wall of the underground's tube. When metropolitan train passes through them at a certain specified speed, they form a marvelous video sequence in the train carriage window. The beauty of this system lies in its simplicity -- no electronics, flashing lights, sensors or moving parts, except for the passing train. It's a natural environment kind of advertising, because you have a captive audience of thousands of passengers who are looking for something to do. It is an exploratory study conducted to understand the impact of transit authorities and advertisers on decision making process. This paper intends to understand the importance of In-tunnel advertising. The research reveals that the influence of visual representation as In-tunnel advertising has the great potential to change the advertising scenario in the near future.*

Keywords: *in-tunnel advertising, metro train, entertainment media*

I. Introduction

In-tunnel advertising is a great, creative and innovative advertising idea. An in-tunnel advertising system consists of series of back-lit poster images to create the illusion of a motion picture advertisement screened in the train carriage window. These posters with consecutive frames of a movie are hanged out next to each other on the wall of the underground's tube. When metropolitan train passes through them at a certain specified speed, they form a marvelous video sequence in the train carriage window.

This is achieved through a series of backlit posters, each one a frame of video, with 24 frames per one second of display. Controlled by our patented operating software, each poster is flashed by xenon lamps in exactly the right position to centre the image in the window of the train. The accompanying video simulation demonstrates the principle. The idea of lighting posters in tunnels to capture the attention of train passengers is not new. Indeed the original patent dates back to 1909. Making the image clearer and stable however a more complex is task and requires high quality and accurate control systems. An earlier version of this type of technology was developed by the In-tunnel directors for the Motion poster Company in early 2000. Since then In-tunnel has completely redeveloped the product to make it extremely reliable with low maintenance costs. Production costs are now in line or well below other types of

tunnel and station advertising hardware.

II. Literature Review

Ashok K. Rajpal (2000) studied about Washington Metropolitan Area Transit Authority Tunnel Advertising (WMATA) which seeked the services of a competent contractor to provide and operate a revenue-producing, state-of-the-art advertising program in the tunnels of the Metrorail system based on the concept of creating an illusion of motion with a stationary panel system. Passengers on the moving rail vehicles will view the advertising panels through the car windows as the train passes through the tunnels. The contractor shall do everything necessary at the contractor's expense in consideration of the right to sell and operate the revenue-producing tunnel advertising program, which right is granted herein. The Tunnel Advertising Program shall not interfere with WMATA's transportation system operation, safety, maintenance or with WMATA's signal and communications systems.

Louis M. Brill (2002) presented a paper on Outdoor advertising which has given a new print direction to subway in-tunnel advertising. The new medium is championed by several advertising firms, particularly Manhattan-based outdoor advertising firm Sub media and Winnipeg, Manitoba-based Sidetrack Technology. A low-tech approach to subway displays in subway tunnels, in-tunnel advertising relies on a scientific phenomenon known as

persistence of vision, which allows humans to see animated or moving pictures. In this process, a continuous strip of slightly varying pictures is transferred to a film strip. When the film is projected, the mind records each image as a continuous movement. The concept of in-tunnel advertising was inspired by a zoetrope.

L. Müller & F. Pacher (2005) studied about advanced image placement system that adjusts in real time to train speed variations. Systems are controlled and monitored via the internet. Train statistics are reported in real time to operator. Excellent image quality appears precisely where desired and it does not interfere with cell phone networks.

Joseph A. Caruso et.al (2004) analyzed the synthesis of transit practice decisions which face many issues such as whether should they sell advertisements in-house or contract out the function? If contracted, what should be the contract terms and how should a request for proposals be structured? What types of displays should they sell? Should they pursue nontraditional forms of advertising such as bus and train wraps, station dominance, in-vehicle and in-station video screens, and electronic signs and in-tunnel advertising? Should they accept non-commercial and public service advertising? How can the agency avoid becoming enmeshed in controversy over advertisements that address emotionally charged issues such as abortion and other sexual topics or that portray graphic violence? How should staff strike a balance between maximizing revenues and using advertising space to promote the agency and help the community through public service advertisements? This report documents and summarizes transit agencies experience with advertising sales and synthesizes current practices for advertising sales, contracting, and display. This information can help agency staff address these issues and implement effective advertising programs.

III .Research Methodology

3.1 Statement of Problem:

For underground mass transit systems In-tunnel advertising is a great, creative and innovative advertising idea. An in-tunnel advertising system consists of series of back-lit poster images to create the illusion of a motion picture advertisement screened in the train carriage window.

IV .Data Analysis

4.1 Testing of hypothesis:

Table 1: Showing the Testing of Hypothesis for prominence of in-tunnel advertising

Hypothesis	Level of Significance	Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Accepted/Rejected
Impact of in-tunnel advertising is prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.	5%	3.57	0.052	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
People will enjoy in-tunnel advertising.	5%	0.043	0.149	Null Hypothesis is accepted
Visual representation is not better than still representation.	5%	0.005	0.073	Null Hypothesis is accepted

Transit systems are seeking new sources of revenue to fund their operations.

3.2 Research Objectives:

1. To ascertain pilot study opinion or impression about tunnel advertising in Bangalore.
2. To ascertain the opinion of the consumer about tunnel advertising.
3. To create awareness about the revolutionary In-tunnel advertising.
4. To understand the In-tunnel advertising marketing system.
5. To get updated with the innovative trends of advertising.

3.3 Hypothesis:

H0: Impact of in-tunnel advertising is prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

H1: Impact of in-tunnel advertising is not prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

3.4 Primary Data:

Primary data has been collected using a questionnaire and personal interview which covered various dimensions of the research questions. Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data for the research. The sample size consisted of 60 respondents who are commuters of metro and are mainly working professionals, students and public sector professionals.

3.5 Secondary Data:

Secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature and other relevant documents. Magazines, Journals, Fact sheets and Web resources, online libraries and websites are other sources.

3.6 Statistical Techniques used

Chi square test:

The application of chi square test in this study was to determine whether their exists relationship between the expected frequencies and the observed frequencies in one or more categories. The test was also used to find out whether the in-tunnel advertising is prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

4.2 Interpretation:

1. H0: Impact of in-tunnel advertising is prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

H1: Impact of in-tunnel advertising is not prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

Since the p-value is lesser than 5% level of significance, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that Impact of in-tunnel advertising is not prominent over other techniques used in order to advertise for metro travelers.

2. H0: People will enjoy in-tunnel advertising.

H1: People will not enjoy in-tunnel advertising.

Since the p-value is greater than 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that People will enjoy in-tunnel advertising.

3. H0: Visual representation is not better than still representation.

H1: Visual representation is better than still representation.

Since the p-value is greater than 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative is rejected. In other words, we can conclude that Visual representation is not better than still representation.

V .Findings

- According to the research majority of the people believe that visual representation more eye catchy. Some people also believe that visual representation has high convincing ability and using that high viewership can be achieved. And some people also believe with visual representation better branding can be done.
- According to the research majority of the people prefer advertisement on TV. Some people like advertisement on radio, newspaper, and magazine also.
- According to the survey most of the people see the advertisement during the travelling time, on hording, posters, and billboards and sometimes on trade show and leaflets.
- According to the survey most of the people's past time during travelling is listening music. Other than that their pass time are window gazing, looking ads, reading books and sometimes busy with mobiles also.
- According to the research majority of the people believe metro train will have an impact on 2wheelers, and as well as 4 wheelers and public transporters. It will have little impact on auto rickshaw also. Some of the respondents believe that there will not be any impact.
- According to the research majority of the people believe that metro train will be safer, quick, and convenient. And some people also believe it is part of entertainment also.
- 7. According to the research majority of the people believe that because of heavy traffic metro train is

in Bangalore and rest most of the people believe the reason of metro train because of too much crowd, too much private car, too many two wheelers and one of the reason also it is a Tech city.

- Visual representations are more eye catchy. It has high convincing ability and using that high viewership can be achieved. Using visual representation better branding can be done.
- Majority of the people prefer advertisement on TV. Some people like advertisement on radio, newspaper, and magazine also.
- During the travel time most of the people see the advertisement, on hording, posters, and billboards and sometimes on trade show and leaflets.
- Majority of the people believe that metro train will be safer, quick, convenient and lesser traffic. And some people also believe it is part of entertainment also.
- Because of heavy traffic metro train is in Bangalore and the other reason of metro train because of too much crowd, too much private car, too many two wheelers and one of the reasons also it is a Tech city.

VI .Suggestions

- In-tunnel advertising will be very effective in future.
- It's a new technology and people are not sure about this technology.
- People will enjoy advertisement in metro.
- In-tunnel of metro train will be used for advertising and people are looking forward to see that kind of advertising.
- Most of the people spent time on travel 1-3 hrs per day.
- Most of the people spent money on travel RS. 20-50 per day.
- Most of the people very much interested to travel in metro.
- Majority of the people believe that metro train will be safer, quick, and convenient.
- Metro train will have an impact on 2wheelers, and as well as 4 wheelers and public transporters also. It will have little impact on auto rickshaw also.
- Entry of metro train will affect on auto rickshaw, and as well as there will some effect on taxi, buses and cabs. Some people also believe that there will not be any impact.

VII .Conclusion

The research give us a quite view of advertising, how it effective in business. Doing this research we can understand completely visual representation of advertising is effective than other advertising procedure. People enjoy visual representation of advertising. The In-tunnel advertising is a new technology people are looking forward to see this kind of advertising in Bangalore metro tunnel. So In-tunnel advertising will be effective in Bangalore as well as in other cities of India.

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